

CUSTOMER RETENTION AFTER PRODUCT SALES

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INTRODUCTION

Every company wants to make the product in such a way that it can fulfill all the demands of the customer and it shows by the customer retention after the sale of the product means if a buyer likes the product, then they will again come to purchase the same product without judging its quality because now they have faith on the given product. So, this is the key concept of any business that to satisfy the customer once and then your products demand will automatically increase. It can also help to build good relations with the customer. It means you are not just selling a product but giving value to your customer that's another level that is beyond business and it's like a family relationship with the customer.

UNDERSTAND THE TERM CUSTOMER RETENTION

Customer retention doesn't mean that customers buy products just 2-3 times but it means if the customer is habitual of buying your product again and again and it is continuing for many years it means you have gained customer retention. This means now your customer is more loyal towards you.

$$\text{Customer Retention Rate} = \frac{\text{Customers at the end of the period} - \text{New customers}}{\text{Customers at the beginning of the period}} \times 100$$

Fig. 1: Customer retention rate formula

According to this formula, we can calculate the customer retention in which we need some data like a customer at the beginning of the period and new customer and customer at the end of the period and by putting all these values we can get the customer retention rate which helps to grow the business easily.

HOW TO INCREASE CUSTOMER RETENTION?

We should always work upon good planning and that is the soul of any business to make the right strategy to get more success so here we are going to discuss some strategies which will increase customer retention in the business.

1) Good communication with the customer

If we don't communicate with our family and friends for a long period even, they used to forget us and we feel like we don't know each other so it shows that communication in any relationship is essential and thus the relation between customer and company will be healthy enough if they will keep in touch with each other through various methods. Send the customer birthday greetings so that they will feel homely because it will give them extra happiness that you remember their birthday. Try to organize some giveaway scheme in which you can select some of your lucky customers through a lucky draw and can give them some product for free of cost it will create a very positive impact on your customers.

2) The first impression should be good enough

When customer purchase product for the first time and they feel that not only the product is good but also, we get good product services I think this strategy create a positive impact on the customer and this is called the first impression is the last impression because now you have gained the faith on customer and they are now bound to come to your place because they don't want to compromise with quality.

3) Easy process for the customer

As we all know that nowadays everyone wants to buy products from Amazon. They work a very smooth way means you just need to click on a product and add it into the cart

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and just pay the bill through your credit card or any other payment method but this process is so easy and time-saving that everyone wants to buy their favorite and daily life products from amazon and their delivery service are also very reliable you will get the product on time before delivery they will make sure that you are at home means before they reach to your door they will ask you on the phone that whether you are at home or not and will take your digital signature to assure that the product they are delivering is in right hands and if there is any defect in the product they will replace it I think if the work is so perfect then nobody can deny buying the product from such reliable site.

4) Survey for the product

Always try to know the problem of your customer by surveying your product for this you can use an online platform like nowadays many people watch You Tube so companies display their survey as an advertisement and thus people before watching their favorite video they watch survey and sometimes give the reply which will help to assess that which product they like the most and from which company they prefer to buy this product you can also go through its benefit and can put some value on your product. The survey always helps to understand the demand of the customer and to make your product better which can fulfill the expectation of the customer.

5) Gift for returning customer

This small effort can give a big profit and good connection with your customer it doesn't mean that you need to give expensive products to your customer sometimes small but valuable things work the most because they can fulfill their need. Customer when coming next time for buying the product and they see that they are getting some reward for the next time shopping they spread this news to their family members, friends, and neighbors which can help to increase your customers and they also do mouth publicity for you just because you are good enough with them and well behave always create benefit for us.

6) Advertisement through the bag

Whenever a customer comes to the shop and when they buy the product always pack them into a bag on which you can advertise for your shop like to design a bag in such a

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way that it is good in quality and make sure that you have provided your shop name and mobile and shop number and address of the shop so that whenever they go people will see the bag and can read the shop name and they can also reach to the shop very easily.

7) Buy one get one free scheme

Always try to come up with some new ideas that can attract customers towards the shop and some time these schemes work great that if the customer is not in a need of any product, then also, they want to buy it because of the good scheme and they think that it is for a limited time and if they will not purchase this product now then they can miss the big opportunity.

8) Get product feedback

Customer can only provide genuine feedback of your product because they have used it whether it is a daily use product or an electronic item when they use it they can tell you the pros and cons of the product and when you ask for feedback it makes them feel valuable because you care for their opinion and want to improve your product as much as possible and this is the right way to make your product number one in the market.

Fig 2: Customer retention model

CONCLUSION

It is necessary to connect with the customer either through direct communication means to try to call them or send an email about your new offers and also give rewards when they come next time for the purchase these are the ideas that impress every kind of customer. Customer retention is a long-term process we can't change everything overnight. The right strategy toward a goal is a must so the points we have discussed above are necessary in the real world to get good results.

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